

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

A. OKURA* J. INAGAKI** E. NAKATA**
S. IKEGAMI*** T. OHSAKI*** M. YOSHIDA***

* Associate Prof. Institute of Industrial Science Univ. of Tokyo 22-1, Roppongi 7 chome, Minato-ku, Tokyo, 106 Japan

** Graduate Student & Prof. The Casting Research Lab. Waseda Univ. 8-26, Nishiwaseda 2 chome, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo 160 Japan

*** Research and Development Division, Toho Beslon Comp. 234, Kamitogari, Nagaizumi-cho, Sunto-gun, Shizuoka Pref., 411 Japan

The mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced 5056 aluminium matrix composites, which were prepared by the ion-plating and vacuum hot-pressing technique (this technique were developed by research and development division in Toho Beslon Comp.), were measured at room temperature and at elevated temperatures. Young's modulus measured at room temperature was close to rule-of-mixtures value.

The longitudinal tensile tests have shown that most of the measured values of room temperature tensile strength of the composites were lower than those calculated by the rule-of-mixtures and the best result was $\sim 61 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ representing ~ 78 per cent rule-of-mixtures at ~ 33 per cent volume fraction of fiber. At elevated temperature, the longitudinal tensile strength of composite was slightly degraded up to 450°C and remarkable fell off at 550°C .

The transverse tensile strength was generally much lower than expected.

The mode of failures at elevated temperature has been studied by optical and scanning electron microscopy of fractured and etched composite specimens. The observations have shown that the weak grain boundary of the matrix governed the mode of failure. The high temperature failure of the composite was generally accompanied by a shear crack. This crack was likely to initiate at the contract point of fibers or at the other defects in the composite and propagate mainly along the grain boundary of matrix at 550°C , in contrast will along the fiber-matrix interface at lower temperature.

Introduction

Previous studies on fiber reinforced composite materials have concentrated on the development of the materials with high strength to density and modulus to density ratios. The major part of this development has taken place in the field of fiber reinforced plastics because of their simplicity of fabrications and excellent properties obtained.

But recent demands for fiber reinforced composite materials for use at high temperature have prompted the development of metal matrix composites. Because of their potential for the above mentioned properties, considerable interest has generated in carbon fiber reinforced aluminium composites. Two principal barriers, however, to the successful development of carbon-aluminium composites exist. One is aluminium carbide (Al_4C_3) formation at the surface of the fibers after long time exposure at temperature greater than $550^\circ C$. (1)(2) The other is difficulty in wetting carbon with liquid aluminium.

To overcome those difficulties, several techniques have been used for fabricating carbon-aluminium composites.

Pepper, et al, (3)(4) prepared graphite fiber reinforced Al-Si eutectic alloy composites by using an infiltration and liquid phase hot pressing technique, and reported longitudinal tensile strength of $\sim 101 kg/mm^2$ * with ~ 28 per cent V.f.. Jackson, et al, (5) obtained tensile strength value of $\sim 56 kg/mm^2$ * representing ~ 80 per cent rule-of-mixtures at ~ 30 per cent V.f., using graphitised and carbonised fiber-aluminium matrix composites prepared by vapor deposition. Morita, et al, (6) prepared chemically nickel pre-coated carbon fiber-aluminium composites and reported tensile strength of $\sim 9.5 kg/mm^2$ at $600^\circ C$. There is thus a wide range of variability in strength of composites prepared by various techniques.

On the other hand, the fracture behavior of the carbon fiber-aluminium matrix composites at elevated temperature is not necessarily revealed.

In this paper, therefore, we will discuss the mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced 5056 aluminium alloy composites, which were prepared by the ion-plating and vacuum hot-pressing technique, and observations on the mode of failure of the composites mainly at elevated temperature.

Experimental Method

1. Measurements of Mechanical Properties

Volume fraction of fiber was determined by measuring density and weight of each composite panels. The specimens were then cut from each panels, and tested as follows.

1.1 Measurement of Young's modulus

The measurements of Young's modulus at room temperature were performed by the two point suspended vibration test developed for measurements on reinforced plastic specimens. The shape of specimen was generally 80mm long \times 0.8mm thick \times 10mm wide.

1.2 Longitudinal Tensile Tests

Actual dimensions of the test specimen was: parallel gauge section, 10mm: gauge width, 2.5mm: thickness, 0.8mm and radius of curvature, 8mm. The grips of all specimens were chemically coated by nickel to prevent the failure in the grip section. The tests were performed at room temperature, $300^\circ C$, $450^\circ C$ and $550^\circ C$ in a vacuum of $\sim 2 \times 10^{-4}$ Torr. Using an UNION opt. Co. high temperature tensile testing machine. The test temperature was measured by a P.R. thermocouple attached to the center of the specimen. The specimens were soaked for 15 min. at a fixed temperature to ensure temperature equilibrium prior to testing. The cross head speed was $\sim 1 mm/min$.

* maximum tensile strength

1.3 Transverse Tensile Tests

The shape of specimens was : gauge length, 10mm ; gauge width, 3mm ; thickness, 1.5mm. And the grip section was also coated by nickel. The tests were performed at room temperature and at 550°C. The other testing conditions were the same as those of longitudinal tensile tests.

1.4 Observations of Fracture Surface and Transverse Microstructure

Some of tensile specimens (both longitudinal and transverse tests) were examined by scanning electron microscopy after testing. And on some longitudinal tensile specimens, a transverse surface was metallographically etched by HF/C₂H₅OH/CH₃OH solution and was examined by optical microscopy.

Results and Discussion

1. Mechanical Properties of Composites at Room Temperature

The effect of the volume fraction of fiber on the room temperature Young's modulus is shown in Fig.1. Most of the measured values were lower than those calculated by the rule-of-mixtures but increased with increasing V.f. in response to the rule-of-mixtures.

The longitudinal tensile strength of composites is shown plotted as a function of V.f. in Fig.2. In terms of per cent rule-of-mixtures strength, the best result represented ~ 78 per cent rule-of-mixtures value at ~ 33 per cent V.f.. The deviation of longitudinal tensile strength is greater than that of Young's modulus. Such a deviation seems to be caused by misalignment of the fibers or by macro defects in the composite. In this investigation practically, a small defect domain which was free from carbon fiber was observed on the fracture surface of the specimen showing remarkably low strength. And in the specimen that showed high strength, fiber distribution in the transverse section of the composite was comparatively uniform. Further improvement of mechanical properties will be achieved by improving the fiber alignment and distribution in the composite.

2. Longitudinal Tensile Strength at Elevated Temperature

The temperature dependency of the longitudinal tensile strength is shown in Fig.3. Macroscopic observation of the fracture surface shows that most of the spe-

Fig.1 Young's modulus of composites as a function of V.f.. Rule-of-mixtures line is also indicated.

Fig.2 Longitudinal tensile strength of composites as a function of V.f.. Rule-of-mixtures line is also indicated.

Fig.3 Degradation of the longitudinal tensile strength of composites as a function of test temperature.

cimens tested at low temperature failed at parallel gauge section. At 550°C, however, considerable number of specimens broken in the grip section by cracking parallel to the fiber direction; such data were omitted in Fig.3. In addition to giving a more jagged fracture path, the specimens tested at 550°C also exhibited a much greater degree of fiber pull-out.

The transverse microstructure of an etched specimen tested at room temperature is illustrated in Fig.4 (a). The grain boundary of the matrix is clearly visible. The double structures of the grain boundary of the matrix are due to ion-plating process: fibers passed the process two times to controll the volume fraction of fiber. Such double structures observed in ion-plated carbon fiber are shown in Fig.4 (c). Fig.4 (b) shows the microstructure of specimen tested at 550°C. In this figure, the inner grain boundary of matrix is not clear. This indicates that the matrix has already started to recrystallize during the test. It seems that such recrystallization of the matrix and difference of the thermal expansion coefficient between carbon fiber and aluminium matrix relieve the bonding stress acted at the fiber-matrix interface and cause a large quantity of fiber pull-out at 550°C.

Typical scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surface of the composite tested at room temperature are illustrated in Fig.5. The surface shows the fiber pull-outs in some degree.(Fig.5 (a), (b)) But most of the fracture surface is covered with the granulated structure shown in Fig.5 (c). The ductile behavior of the matrix can be seen in the form of necking.(Fig.5 (b)) Fig.6 shows the typical fracture surface of specimen tested at 550°C. It is obvious that the matrix failed in a fully ductile manner (Fig.6 (a)) and the interlaminar shear fracture which was frequently seen in the fracture surface of specimens tested at 550°C occurred at the

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.4 Optical micrograph of the transverse microstructures of composites tested at (a) R.T., (b) 550°C, and (c) the transverse cross sections of ion-plated carbon fibers.

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

(c)

(c)

Fig.5 Scanning electron micrograph of the typical fracture surface of the composite tested at R.T.

Fig.6 Scanning electron micrograph of the typical fracture surface of the composite tested at 550°C.

(a)

(b)

Fig.7 Optical micrograph of the transverse microstructure of interlaminar shear fractured composite tested at 550°C.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig.8 Scanning electron micrograph of the typical fracture surface after transverse tensile testing at (a), (b) R.T. and (c), (d) 550°C.

grain boundary of the matrix. (Fig.6 (b), (c)) And the fibers pull-out is also seen.

The optical micrographs of the interlaminar shear fractured specimen are shown in Fig.8. The crack was likely to initiate at the contact points of fibers (Fig.7 (a)) and propagate along the grain boundary of the matrix. (Fig.7 (b))

3. Transverse Tensile Strength

The transverse tensile strength of the composites was much lower than expected. The average strength obtained at room temperature was $\sim 2.1 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ at ~ 33 per cent V.f.. Fig.8 shows the typical fracture surface of a transverse tensile specimen tested at room temperature ((a), (b)) and at 550°C ((c), (d)).

The surfaces of the carbon fibers are clearly visible with little or no aluminum matrix materials adhering to them in Fig.8 (a) and the fracture seems to occur at fiber-matrix interfaces. (Fig.8 (b)) But Fig.8 (c) shows that the transverse tensile failure of the composite tested at 550°C occurs mainly at the grain boundary of the matrix. No segregation of magnesium was found at the grain boundary of the matrix by electron probe microanalysis.

4. Mode of Failures

Optical and scanning electron microscopy of failed and etched composite specimens have provided information on the mode of failure of the composite in tension. As shown in Fig.6 (b) and (c), the failure of the composite is accompanied by a shear failure at elevated temperature. The crack seems to initiate at the contact point of fibers or at the other defects in the composite and propagate along the grain boundary of matrix in contrast with along the fiber-matrix interface at lower temperature. The results indicate that the strength of fiber-matrix bonding that is weaker than that of the matrix grain-boundary at lower temperature becomes stronger than that of the grain boundary at elevated temperature. It seems that the relief of the bonding stress acted at fiber-matrix interface by recrystallization of matrix and the weakened strength of the grain boundary of matrix cause a drastic degradation in the longitudinal tensile strength at elevated temperature. Fig.9 shows the model that we thought out for the tensile failure at lower and elevated temperature.

That is to say, at elevated temperature fibers are permitted to break at the weakest point. (i.e. at the large flaw on the carbon fibers) because of the relief of the bonding stress acted at fiber-matrix interface and then pull-out occurs. And interlaminar shear failure occurs at the grain boundary of matrix is helpful to transmit the axial load carried by the fibers to the weakest point of adjacent fibers.

On the other hand, at lower temperature composite failure occurs at the weakest cross section which is almost perpendicular to the fiber and nearly average value of the strength of fibers contribute to the strength of the composites.

Fig.9 Schematic drawing of a model for the tensile failure at lower and elevated temperature.

Conclusions

The following conclusion can be drawn from the present investigation.

- 1) Carbon fiber-5056 aluminium matrix composite prepared by the ion-plating and vacuum hot pressing technique exhibit Young's modulus that correspond well with those predicted by the rule-of-mixtures.
- 2) Longitudinal tensile strength of the composites at room temperature was lower than those calculated by the rule-of-mixtures and the best result was $\sim 61 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ representing ~ 78 per cent rule-of-mixtures at ~ 33 per cent V.f..
- 3) At elevated temperature, the longitudinal tensile strength of the composites was slightly degraded up to 450°C and remarkably fell off at 550°C . The relief of the bonding stress acted at fiber-matrix interface by recrystallization of matrix and the weak strength of the grain boundary of matrix cause a drastic degradation in the longitudinal tensile strength at elevated temperatures.
- 4) The transverse tensile strength was generally much lower than expected. And the fracture surfaces exhibit the failure at grain boundary at elevated temperature in contrast with at fiber-matrix interface at lower temperature.
- 5) Thus the strength of the grain boundary and the recrystallization of the matrix should be considered carefully when we use the composite at elevated temperature.

Appendix

Strength of Carbon Fiber

Monofilament tensile test was performed at room temperature using an Instron type tensile testing machine. The cross head speed was usually $\sim 0.4 \text{ mm/min}$. The high strength type carbon fiber was investigated in this study. Comparative change in the fiber diameters was observed. We adopted 6.8μ as an average diameter of the fibers by measuring the fiber diameters in the optical micrographs of the transverse cross section of the composite. It should be pointed out that all the fiber properties shown in the following figures were calculated on the basis of this average diameter.

Fig.10 shows the fracture stress of carbon fibers as a function of gauge length. Although there is considerable scatter originated in the diameter distribution of the fibers, a marked size effect is apparent.

In Fig.11, fracture stress of carbon fibers is plotted against the reciprocal

Fig.10 Fracture stress of carbon fibers as a function of gauge length.

Fig.11 Fracture stress of carbon fibers as a function of reciprocal of gauge length.

of gauge length. The strength of the brittle fibers is said to be greatly influenced by the flaws both on the surface and in the interior of the fibers. (7) Fig.11 shows that two different types of dependency exists respectively. In the range of $1/l > 0.25$ (mm^{-1}) (i.e. $l < 4(\text{mm})$)....(A), there is an indication that the average fracture stress of the fibers is inversely proportional to the gauge length and in $1/l < 0.25$ (mm^{-1}) (i.e. $l > 4(\text{mm})$)....(B) the scatter increases with decreasing $1/l$. This indicates that two different types of flaws affect the strength of the carbon fibers. (8) One is fine flaw distributed with high existence probability. The other is large flaw distributed with low existence probability. The former seems to correspond to the small inner holes or cracks, and give upper bound to the strength of fibers. (Fig.11 (A)) And the latter correspond to the large inner holes or cracks both on the surface and in the interior of the fibers that have greater influence on the fiber strength and result in fiber failure at various stress levels. (Fig.11 (B))

(a)

(b)

Fig.12 Scanning electron micrograph of a typical large flaw on the surface of the carbon fiber.

Fig.12 shows such a large flaw observed on the surface of the carbon fibers.

References

- (1) G. Blankenburgs ; J. Aust. Inst. Metals, Vol 14 (1969) No.4 p.236
- (2) H. Khan ; Met. Trans., Vo. 7A (1976) p.1281
- (3) R. T. Pepper, J. W. Upp, R. C. Rossi and E. G. Kendall ; Met. Trans., Vol 2 (1971) p.117
- (4) R. T. Pepper and R. A. Penty ; J. Comps. Mater, Vol.8 (1974) p.29
- (5) P. W. Jakson, D. M. Braddick and P. J. Walker ; Fiber Sci. Tech., Vol 5 (1972) p.219
- (6) M. Morita and E. Baba ; J. Japan Inst. Metals., Vol 37 (1973) p.315
- (7) M. Morita, H. Takeda and I. Arima ; J. Japan Inst. Metals., Vol 36 (1972) p.1213
- (8) F. R. Barnet and M. K. Norr ; Composites., April (1976) p.93